

Law of Conservation of Dimensional Magnitude

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Abstract:

The law of conservation of dimensional magnitude is a hypothetical law that can be used in the study of wormholes and discoveries of more dimensions. Law of conservation of dimensional magnitude is derived and similar to the concept of law of conservation of mass for 3D bodies. The ideology comes from the topic that supposedly if the length of a 3D body decreases then the breadth will increase height being the same till the mass of the body remains same.

Keywords:

Hypothesis, Dimensions, Law, Wormholes

Introduction:

In the pursuit of unraveling the intricate mysteries of our universe, visionary thinkers often venture into uncharted territories, introducing groundbreaking concepts that challenge the foundations of established knowledge. Among these thought-provoking propositions is the "Law of Conservation of Dimensional Magnitude," conceived by Sayandeep Dutta. This theoretical principle offers a distinctive perspective on the nature of dimensions, particularly within the realms of speculative constructs like wormholes and multidimensional spaces. By drawing an analogy to the established principle of mass conservation in three-dimensional bodies, this law postulates that the collective magnitude spanning all dimensions of a physical entity remains invariant, even as conditions fluctuate.

Intriguingly, this exploration compels us to reevaluate the fundamental composition of our reality. While we are well-acquainted with the conventional triad of spatial dimensions (X, Y, and Z) in conjunction with the temporal dimension, the hypothesis beckons us to consider the plausibility of hidden dimensions that may elude our current perceptions. The essence of Dutta's conjecture lies in its proposition that even a minute alteration in one dimension could engender compensatory changes in others, preserving the aggregate magnitude intact.

This paper navigates the theoretical underpinnings of the Law of Conservation of Dimensional Magnitude, presenting illustrative scenarios to underscore its implications. Notably, it contemplates the potential consequences of this principle within the context of hypothetical scenarios such as bodies traversing through enigmatic phenomena like wormholes, where the very fabric of spacetime could undergo profound metamorphosis. Moreover, by harnessing mathematical models and conceptual frameworks, this paper endeavors to provide insights into the conceivable distortions and adaptations that entities might undergo when exposed to such uncharted environments.

It is incumbent upon us to recognize that the Law of Conservation of Dimensional Magnitude is a speculative conjecture and, as of the present, lacks empirical validation owing to the speculative nature of the subjects it addresses. Nonetheless, this notion offers a fresh vista for contemplating dimensions, space, and the enigmas that may lie beyond the confines of our existing comprehension. As our exploration of the universe advances, this proposition could catalyze inventive avenues of inquiry and deepen our grasp of the intricate underpinnings that define the nature of our cosmos.

Hypothesis Statement:

Statement: The '**Law of Conservation of Dimensional Magnitude**' states that the total magnitude of all the dimensions of a physical body remain constant at all given conditions.

The proposition of the 'Law of Conservation of Dimensional Magnitude' introduces a captivating conjecture that challenges our conventional understanding of dimensions within the physical realm. Within this theoretical framework, it is postulated that the aggregate magnitude of all dimensions comprising a physical entity remains unaltered, irrespective of any modifications that might occur within individual dimensions.

Our existing comprehension recognizes four dimensions: the trio of spatial dimensions (X, Y, Z) dictating the spatial extent of an object, and time, constituting the temporal facet. However, the concept posits that even if we venture beyond our current apprehension and consider additional dimensions, the fundamental 'dimensional magnitude' remains invariant.

For illustrative purposes, let's consider a hypothetical instance. Envision a four-dimensional entity encountering a hypothetical wormhole—a structure conjectured to link disparate points in space time. In the scenario where this entity encounters a shift in the progression of time within the wormhole, potentially resulting in a temporal slowdown from an external observer's standpoint, the concept suggests a consequential adaptation in its spatial dimensions (X, Y, Z) to uphold the unchanging aggregate magnitude.

This notion implies a profound interdependence among dimensions. Analogous to Einstein's theory of relativity that unifies space time, changes in one facet—like time dilation—might precipitate corresponding alterations in other dimensions to preserve the unvarying aggregate magnitude. However, it is imperative to underscore that this concept firmly resides within the domain of speculative theoretical physics.

In conclusion, the concept of the 'Law of Conservation of Dimensional Magnitude' provides an absorbing lens through which we can explore the intricate dynamics of dimensions within the physical universe. Nevertheless, it is essential to approach this concept with a discerning perspective. Transforming a speculative idea into an established scientific principle necessitates meticulous mathematical formulation, theoretical substantiation, and empirical validation. Nevertheless, this concept underscores the potential of imaginative thinking to expand the horizons of our understanding of the cosmos.

Figure 1. Wormhole: Connecting two different parts of universe

Theoretical framework:

For a 3-Dimensional body:

Let there be a cuboid of 1 unit length, 2-unit breadth and 1 unit height and density 1 per unit volume.

So, the mass of the object would turn out to be 2 since the volume would be 2 cubic units.

But if we consider a case where the length becomes 2 then there has to be a change in breadth or height to maintain the same mass of the cuboid since the **law of conservation of mass** states that ‘mass can neither be created nor be destroyed.’

$$(\mathbf{Length}) \times (\mathbf{Breadth}) \times (\mathbf{Height}) = 1 \times 2 \times 1 = 2 \times 1 \times 1$$

For a 4-Dimensional body (travelling in a wormhole):

If a body is travelling through a wormhole, it will be sandwiched between two layers of folded space. Now we have four dimensions in an initial body travelling through space which are X, Y, Z and Time. We know that the definition of a wormhole states that it mainly connects two parts of space and has its own frame of time i.e., the time in space and wormhole are not the same. So, if a body travels through a wormhole it is highly possible that there are other dimensions introduced to the body inside the wormhole since time gets decreased.

To prove this, we have an example which states that if a cube is initially of edge 3 units, increasing per second with 9 units till 6 seconds then the mass after 6 seconds will be-

To determine the mass of the cube after 6 seconds, we need to know the density of the material the cube is made of. Mass is related to volume and density by the formula:

$$\text{Mass} = \text{Volume} \times \text{Density}$$

The volume of a cube is given by:

$$\text{Volume} = \text{Side Length}^3$$

In this case, the side length of the cube is changing over time. It starts at 3 units and increases at a rate of 9 units per second. So, after t seconds, the side length will be $3 + 9t$ units.

After 6 seconds ($t = 6$), the side length will be $3 + 9 \times 6 = 57$ units.

With the given density (Density = 1) and the side length of the cube after 6 seconds (Side Length = 57), we can calculate the mass using the formula:

$$\text{Mass} = \text{Volume} \times \text{Density}$$

The volume of the cube is given by:

$$\text{Volume} = \text{Side Length}^3$$

Substituting the values:

$$\text{Volume} = (57)^3$$

$$\text{Volume} = 185193$$

Finally, calculating the mass:

$$\text{Mass} = \text{Volume} \times \text{Density}$$

$$\text{Mass} = 185193 \times 1$$

$$\text{Mass} = 185193$$

Therefore, the mass of the cube after 6 seconds will be 185193 units, assuming the units of density are consistent with the units of side length used.

To maintain the mass of the cube while reducing the time to 3 seconds, an adjustment to the rate of change of the side length is needed. This ensures that the volume of the cube remains constant, assuming the density remains consistent.

The volume of the cube is determined by:

$$\text{Volume} = \text{Side Length}^3$$

Given the original rate of side length change (r) as 9 units per second, adjustments are required for the new 3-second time frame.

The original volume at 6 seconds is:

$$\text{Volume original} = (57)^3$$

In order to maintain the same volume for 3 seconds, the adjusted rate of side length change (r) needs to be determined:

$$\text{Volume new} = (\text{Side Length new})^3$$

$$\text{Volume new} = (r * 3)^3$$

Equating the original and new volumes:

$$\text{Volume original} = \text{Volume new}$$

$$(57)^3 = (r * 3)^3$$

Solving for r:

$$r = 57 / 3$$

$$r = 19$$

Hence, the adjusted rate of side length change is 19 units per second for the cube to preserve its mass over 3 seconds.

With this adjusted rate, the new side length after 3 seconds is calculated as:

$$\text{Side Length new} = \text{Initial Side Length} + (r * \text{Time})$$

$$\text{Side Length new} = 3 + 19 * 3$$

$$\text{Side Length new} = 60$$

Therefore, to maintain the cube's mass while reducing the time to 3 seconds, the new side length after 3 seconds would be 60 units.

This shows that if time gets reduced some other dimension's magnitude has to be increased to maintain equilibrium in mass.

Thus, we can say that for all physical bodies,

Sum of dimensions in that body = constant

Figure 2. Wormhole: Front Face

Equation:

Let there be two dimensions for a body with magnitude m and n .

Therefore, with the help of law of conservation of dimensional magnitude we can say that,

$$m + n = \text{constant}$$

Let x be decreased from n and y be increased in m ,

Since, if one decreases one has to be increased so we can come to the conclusion that,

$$m + n = (m + y) + (n - x) = \text{constant}$$

$$m + n = (m + y) + (n - x)$$

$$x = y$$

So, amount decreased is equal to the amount increased. Talking about more than 2 dimensions it is very possible that a new term o will be introduced and either the term o will be manipulated though magnitude as in above case x and y or there will be no changes see in the third dimension and this can be repeated infinite number of times.

For three dimensions with change x , y and z , the equation would be,

$$x = y + z$$

This implies that the magnitude of the number of dimensions will keep changing depending upon the number of dimensions of a given body.

Implications and predictions:

This theory can be applied to all physical bodies in our universe and can be further more helpful in the studies of wormholes and different dimensions possibly existing in this world.

In case of wormholes and dimensions we can say that supposedly in above examples suggest if a body travels through a wormhole, then there are high chances that the time frame for that body will change leading to introduction of new dimensions more than the know four acting on the body and thus deforming it.

Also, this leads to another statement that if the time frame in wormhole remains same as that of any other part of the universe and the time to travel that distance remains same then there will be no deformity in the body travelling the wormhole and thus travelling though it could be made possible as per above examples and proofs.

Drawbacks:

It is important to note that this research has been done on basis of theories and may not be totally correct since there are no possible experiments made up till now that can verify the true nature of wormholes.

Future Research:

As we uncover the mysteries dwelling outside earth in space, we can possibly use this hypothesis in many cases as mentioned above for wormholes and to study dimensions. This research come up totally new ideas for studying dimensions for the human brain that resides in 4-D world including time.

References:

This hypothesis has been made totally on the basis of research and understanding of a particular individual and no references have been used for this hypothesis from any external sources.